

Autistic females' experiences and challenges in psychological and psychiatric care

Palak Jain¹ & Dennis Relajo-Howell²

¹L.S. Raheja College of Arts & Commerce (India)

²University of Edinburgh (United Kingdom)

palakjain1609@gmail.com

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Autistic females often face underdiagnosis and misdiagnosis due to male-centred diagnostic frameworks and sociocultural biases. This study explores their unique challenges in psychological and psychiatric care using thematic analysis of semi-structured interviews with seven participants, including both self-diagnosed and clinically diagnosed individuals. Key findings reveal pervasive dismissal of autistic traits by clinicians, limited understanding of female autism presentations, and reliance on outdated diagnostic tools. Participants highlighted issues such as camouflaging behaviour, financial and bureaucratic barriers to diagnosis, and ineffective therapeutic practices. Despite these challenges, many expressed strong confidence in their self-diagnoses, viewing them as validating and empowering in the absence of formal recognition. The findings underscore the systemic inadequacies within mental health services, which often fail to address the nuanced needs of autistic females. Participants emphasised the importance of clinicians adopting an informed, patient-centred approach that prioritises dialogue, cultural sensitivity, and updated knowledge of autism in females. The study contributes to the growing recognition of self-diagnosis as a valuable, if controversial, avenue for individuals navigating complex healthcare systems. While the sample size limits generalisability, this research highlights urgent gaps in clinical understanding and the need for reform in diagnostic practices. Future studies should explore larger, more diverse samples to deepen understanding of autistic females' lived experiences and examine how self-diagnosis interacts with broader social and clinical dynamics. This work advocates for systemic change to improve outcomes for an underserved and often overlooked population.

Keywords: autism; camouflaging; diagnosis; females; mental health

Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), as defined by the DSM-5, is a neurodevelopmental condition characterised by persistent deficits in social communication, restricted and repetitive behaviours, and atypical sensory processing (Joon et al., 2021). While ASD is widely recognised as a spectrum, significant disparities in diagnosis persist, particularly among females. Much of the existing diagnostic framework is built upon male-centric presentations of autism, which has resulted in a persistent underdiagnosis and misdiagnosis of autistic females (Bargiela et al., 2016). This disparity has far-reaching consequences, as timely diagnosis is critical for accessing appropriate interventions and support systems.

Autistic females often present differently from their male counterparts, exhibiting traits that may not align with traditional diagnostic criteria (Driver & Chester, 2021). These differences include camouflaging behaviours, where individuals consciously or unconsciously mask their autistic traits to conform to societal norms (Hull et al., 2017). Camouflaging, coupled with gendered expectations of social and emotional competence, can obscure the identification of autism in females, leaving many without an accurate diagnosis (Gonçalves Garcia et al., 2025). This phenomenon is further complicated by the biases inherent in widely used diagnostic tools such as the Autism Diagnostic Observation Schedule (ADOS), which lack representative sex-based norms (McPartland et al., 2016).

The implications of these diagnostic challenges extend beyond the clinical setting. Autistic females often encounter dismissive attitudes from clinicians, limited access to tailored interventions, and societal misunderstanding of their lived experiences (Castañeda, 2023). This systemic oversight not only impacts their mental health outcomes but also perpetuates a cycle of misrecognition and neglect within psychological and psychiatric care.

This study seeks to address the pressing gaps in knowledge regarding autistic females' experiences with mental health services. Through thematic analysis of semi-structured interviews, this research aims to explore the barriers faced by both self-diagnosed and clinically diagnosed autistic females in accessing effective care. By amplifying their voices, the study highlights the urgent need for clinicians to adopt more inclusive, patient-centred approaches and calls for systemic reforms in diagnostic and therapeutic practices.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Neurodiversity

The concept of neurodiversity has gained significant traction in contemporary psychology as an alternative to the traditional psychopathological model. First introduced academically by Judy Singer in 1998, neurodiversity shifts the narrative from viewing conditions like Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) as “abnormal” to “atypical” (Walker, 2023). This framework offers a middle ground between the medical and social models of disability, both of which have been criticised for their limited perspectives. Neurodiversity advocates for recognising diverse neurotypes – including conditions like autism and ADHD – as integral to cultural and social stability. This perspective emphasises that fostering neurodiversity benefits society as a whole.

The NHS describes neurodivergent individuals as those whose neurocognitive functioning falls outside the typical range. They request to be understood in terms of the strengths and supports linked to their unique neurocognitive profiles. This conceptual framework is pivotal for contemporary autism research, particularly in exploring individual experiences and strengths rather than focusing solely on deficits.

Autism in females

Despite significant advancements in autism research, gender disparities in diagnosis remain pronounced. The prevalence of autism is consistently higher among males, with studies estimating a male-to-female diagnostic ratio of 2.96 in adults (Posserud et al., 2021). This discrepancy is largely attributed to ascertainment bias, whereby autistic females are underdiagnosed due to the predominance of male-centric diagnostic frameworks (Bargiela et al., 2016).

Autistic females often present with behaviours that differ from the stereotypical male presentation, which can obscure their diagnosis (Napolitano et al., 2022). Camouflaging, the conscious or unconscious masking of autistic traits to “pass” as neurotypical in social settings, is significantly more common among females (Hull et al., 2017). These behaviours, while adaptive in some contexts, can delay diagnosis and increase mental health challenges. Studies also highlight that societal expectations for females to excel in social and emotional intelligence exacerbate this phenomenon, leading to higher rates of camouflaging compared to males (Hull et al., 2018).

Further complicating diagnostic accuracy, autistic females often exhibit internalising behaviours such as anxiety and depression rather than externalising traits like aggression, which are more readily identified in clinical settings (Frazier et al., 2014; Ratto et al., 2018). Additionally, diagnostic tools like the Autism Diagnostic Observation Schedule (ADOS) lack sex-based norms, contributing to the systemic underdiagnosis of females (McPartland et al., 2016).

Another critical factor is the underreporting of autistic traits in females by adults in their environment, such as teachers (Putnam et al., 2024). This lack of recognition further perpetuates diagnostic disparities (Posserud et al., 2018). The need for clinician education is underscored by research indicating that psychotherapists often lack sufficient knowledge to support autistic individuals effectively (Lipinski et al., 2021).

Gender diversity and autism

Emerging research also highlights the intersection between autism and gender diversity. Studies indicate a higher prevalence of autism among transgender and gender-diverse individuals compared to their cisgender counterparts (Warrier et al., 2020). While masking behaviours among non-binary individuals appear similar to those of autistic males and females, current sample sizes are too limited to draw definitive conclusions.

This study acknowledges the importance of inclusivity by incorporating participants who were assigned female at birth but identify with other gender identities. Such an approach aligns with findings that suggest the necessity of considering gender diversity in autism research and practice. These insights have critical implications for the administration of psychological care, as clinicians must account for the unique narratives and experiences of gender-diverse autistic individuals.

In summary, existing literature highlights significant gaps in understanding autism in females and gender-diverse individuals. Biases in diagnostic tools, societal expectations, and clinician training contribute to the systemic underdiagnosis and mistreatment of these populations. Addressing these gaps is essential for fostering a more inclusive and accurate approach to autism diagnosis and care (Relajo & Pilao, 2018).

METHODOLOGY

This study adopts a social constructivist approach, which posits that reality is experienced and understood differently across individuals. The primary aim was to explore the under-researched

experiences of autistic females and integrate these insights into broader public and clinical understandings of autism.

A total of seven participants were recruited for the study, consisting of four self-diagnosed and two clinically diagnosed autistic individuals. Four participants were assigned female at birth (AFAB) but identified with other gender identities. Their inclusion was justified by their socialisation as females and their female-typical anatomy, which aligned with the study's focus on biological and sociocultural factors influencing psychiatric care for females. Participants represented diverse ethnicities, nationalities, socioeconomic classes, and cultural backgrounds.

Individual semi-structured interviews were conducted via online video calls to accommodate participants' geographical and personal needs. All interviews were recorded for transcription purposes, with confidentiality maintained by anonymising participants using initials (e.g., MF). In cases where video calls were not feasible due to technical issues or participants' sensory needs, audio-only recordings were used. Two interview recordings were excluded from the study due to technical corruption, leaving five interviews for analysis.

The interviews explored three overarching themes: a) the female autistic experience, b) experiences with psychiatric clinicians, and c) the perceived importance and impact of a diagnosis. The interviewer, a female psychology researcher with a background in neurodiversity, conducted all interviews and thematic analysis. This shared demographic background contributed to participant comfort and disclosure but also introduced potential bias.

The study employed Braun and Clarke's six-phase framework for thematic analysis (Braun et al., 2023), which involved iterative coding and thematic identification from verbatim interview transcripts. This approach allowed for inductive exploration, which is particularly suited for emerging areas of research. Efforts were made to ground findings in participant quotes to maintain analytical integrity.

While paraphrasing and empathic reflections were used to build rapport, the researcher acknowledges the unbalanced power dynamic inherent in the interviewer-participant relationship. This dynamic, along with the quasi-therapeutic nature of some interactions, may have introduced subtle biases that shaped the findings.

The thematic analysis process aimed to minimise researcher preconceptions by maintaining a rigorous, systematic approach. Nevertheless, findings are recognised as being co-constructed through the active and passive interpretations of participant communications.

In summary, the chosen methodology, including the use of thematic analysis, facilitated a nuanced exploration of autistic females' experiences while acknowledging inherent limitations such as sample size, potential interviewer bias, and the loss of two data sources due to technical issues.

RESULTS

The thematic analysis of participant interviews revealed several key themes and subthemes that illustrate the complexities of autistic females' experiences with identity, clinical interactions, and diagnostic processes. These findings are summarised in Figure 1 and explored in detail below.

Figure 1
Themes and subthemes identified through thematic analysis of participant data

Theme 1: Experience and perception of autism

Autistic traits

Participants identified several traits they strongly associated with their autistic experience, including difficulties in social interaction, sensory sensitivities, and repetitive behaviours. Many reported challenges in interpreting social cues, which often led to misunderstandings and social exhaustion. Sensory sensitivities, such as heightened reactivity to noise and textures, were also a recurrent theme. Several participants discussed their reliance on stimming behaviours, such as hand flapping or rocking, as a means of emotional regulation. A strong preference for routine and predictability was another defining trait, with participants expressing distress when faced with unexpected changes.

One participant, CP, described their struggles with nonverbal communication, stating: "I have a hard time with facial expressions. I do like a lot of... I'm weird with eye contact. I have a timer in my head when I'm talking to people where I'm thinking about, like, having to make eye contact and how I have to think that now I need to look across the room and then consciously decide to move my face in certain ways, which is... exhausting, and leads to a lot of missing what's going on, because I'm focusing so hard on how I look." Similarly, SS highlighted the impact of sensory sensitivities: "I have to wear my headphones in public 'cause I don't like loud sounds... If there's too much noise, I get really irritable and can't focus."

These responses illustrate the profound ways in which sensory and social challenges shape the experiences of autistic females, often leading to additional stress and difficulty navigating everyday interactions.

Autistic joy

Despite these difficulties, participants overwhelmingly described a strong sense of "Autistic Joy," whereby they recognised autism as a fundamental and meaningful aspect of their identity. Many participants expressed appreciation for traits such as heightened creativity, deep empathy, and the ability to engage intensely with special interests. AO reflected on this experience, stating: "Um... I think it's inherently joyful." SS elaborated further: "...It just affects the way I experience joy and love and, you know, like special interests. Special interests are probably like the main thing, that I wouldn't trade for the world. So—like if there was a cure for Autism, that would be – I would never – I couldn't imagine not having special interests, not feeling that strongly."

These statements underscore the complexity of autistic identity, wherein individuals acknowledge the difficulties associated with autism while also embracing the unique ways in which it enriches their lives.

Concurrent ADHD and OCD

Many participants reported co-occurring conditions, particularly ADHD and OCD. The majority had been diagnosed with ADHD, while approximately half had received an OCD diagnosis. Several participants noted that their ADHD diagnosis came before their autism diagnosis, though they felt ADHD alone did not fully explain their experiences. CP commented: "ADHD explained some things, but it wasn't enough. Once I started reading about autism, everything made sense."

This aligns with existing literature, which identifies a high rate of co-occurrence between autism, ADHD, and OCD in females, particularly those who present with high-masking traits.

Theme 2: Experiences with clinicians

Dismissal by clinicians

A pervasive theme among participants was the dismissal of autistic traits by clinicians, often influenced by outdated gendered stereotypes. Many recounted instances where they were told that autism primarily affects males, with some even being explicitly informed that autism is a "boy problem". Others were denied an autism diagnosis because they were able to make eye contact or maintain friendships, despite growing research indicating that these traits are not definitive exclusions for autism, particularly in females.

CP recalled a conversation with a clinician: "People would be like, 'Well you can't have autism because you don't have this set of traits that typically only appear in people who are socialised as men.'" Similarly, AO described an interaction in which a clinician dismissed both her ADHD and autism concerns:

"She said, 'No, you can't have ADHD cause you get decent grades.' And then she said, 'Nah, you can't really be Autistic 'cause you make eye contact and you have a lot of friends.'"

Some participants also shared experiences of misdiagnosis, where clinicians attributed their symptoms to Bipolar Disorder, Cluster B personality disorders, or generalised Anxiety. These findings suggest a systemic issue wherein autistic traits in females are frequently overlooked, misinterpreted, or pathologised under different diagnoses.

Ineffectiveness of talk therapy

Several participants expressed frustration with traditional talk therapy, stating that it failed to address their specific needs as autistic individuals. Many found that therapy sessions focused primarily on self-awareness rather than providing practical strategies for managing autistic-related challenges.

SS noted: "You know, I go in and the things she tells me, tries to teach me, I already read about on my own and I'm already doing, so it just feels a little bit... useless, I guess?" Similarly, CP reflected on their experience:

"I'm really self-aware about things, and talk therapy isn't really it."

One participant reported more success with Eye Movement Desensitisation and Reprocessing (EMDR) therapy, indicating that alternative therapeutic approaches may be more beneficial for autistic individuals.

Theme 3: Feelings about diagnosis

Validation and legitimacy of diagnosis

Participants widely agreed that obtaining a formal autism diagnosis was a validating experience that legitimised their self-perceptions. Many expressed that an official diagnosis helped them communicate their needs to family members, educators, and employers. RA explained: "...Very few people know, and there has been no change in how they treat me now. It just makes more sense to them." JK added: "And I feel like if I had the diagnosis, you know, they would be able to understand, and they could be more at ease 'cause they're like, 'Okay, it, you know, is not that—is a problem, this is just how she is.'"

Formal diagnoses were also considered essential for accessing academic and workplace accommodations, reinforcing the practical significance of diagnostic recognition.

Reasons for no diagnosis

For self-diagnosed participants, financial and bureaucratic barriers were the primary obstacles to obtaining a formal diagnosis. CP described the process as both expensive and time-consuming: "It's just like a whole day, and it's like a lot of money and it's like a whole thing, so I haven't had the bandwidth to do it yet." SS echoed these concerns, stating: "...Bad experiences in the past, and, um, there's a lot of other medical issues going on right now that I'm trying to figure out first. And, uh, financial barriers."

Basis for self-diagnosis

Most self-diagnosed participants reported engaging in extensive independent research, including reading academic literature and consulting autistic communities online. Several described social media as their first introduction to autism beyond mainstream stereotypes. SS recounted: "It wasn't until I was 15 or maybe 16. I kept seeing posts and stuff on my feed on Instagram and other social media. So, that's when I started really seriously looking into it, besides just posts and stuff."

The findings highlight the systemic barriers in autism diagnosis and mental health care for autistic females. While participants expressed strong autistic identity and joy, they also faced widespread clinical dismissal, misdiagnosis, and inaccessible diagnostic pathways. These results emphasise the need for greater clinician awareness, reform in diagnostic frameworks, and improved accessibility of autism evaluations.

DISCUSSION

The findings of this study align with existing literature on the underdiagnosis and misdiagnosis of autistic females while also introducing new insights into the lived experiences of both self-diagnosed and clinically diagnosed individuals. A particularly disheartening theme that emerged was the systemic dismissal of autistic traits in individuals assigned female at birth (AFAB), especially among those who were self-diagnosed. Participants frequently reported encountering clinician biases that directly contradicted contemporary understandings of autism, with reasons for dismissal including statements such as “too pretty”, “too self-aware”, “has a friend”, and “performs too well academically”. These responses reflect a deeply ingrained stereotypical perception of both autism and femininity, wherein autistic traits are still primarily understood through a male-centric lens.

This study reinforces prior research indicating that autistic females are often required to present with more severe impairments before being taken seriously in clinical settings. Many participants expressed frustration at having displayed autistic traits for years without recognition from mental health professionals. Instead, several were misdiagnosed with Bipolar Disorder, Borderline Personality Disorder, or Anxiety Disorders, reflecting a pattern found in other studies on the misclassification of autism in females. The issue of camouflaging – where autistic individuals consciously or unconsciously mask their traits to conform to social expectations – appears to be a significant factor in diagnostic challenges, reinforcing findings that suggest autistic females exhibit higher levels of social masking than their male counterparts.

Beyond issues of diagnostic exclusion, this study highlights significant concerns about the effectiveness of talk therapy for autistic individuals. Many participants reported that traditional therapeutic models failed to address their needs, with sessions often centring on self-awareness rather than offering practical strategies for navigating autistic-related challenges. This aligns with literature suggesting that mainstream psychotherapeutic approaches, which are typically designed for neurotypical individuals, may not be optimally structured for autistic clients. The dissatisfaction expressed by participants suggests an urgent need for autism-informed therapy, with practitioners trained in recognising and accommodating the specific cognitive and emotional needs of autistic individuals.

A significant contribution of this study is its exploration of the experiences of self-diagnosed autistic individuals, a group often overlooked in autism research. The inclusion of these participants challenges the circular inclusion criteria that dominate traditional autism studies, where only those with a formal diagnosis are included, thereby excluding individuals who may have been overlooked due to clinician biases. The findings indicate that self-diagnosed participants exhibited a high correlation with clinically recognised autistic traits and displayed a thorough understanding of the diagnostic criteria. These individuals did not appear to be seeking monetary or social benefits from adopting the label, nor did they exhibit signs of malingering. Instead, many engaged in extensive self-education, often consulting academic literature and autistic communities before arriving at their self-diagnoses.

This raises important questions about the validity of self-diagnosis as a meaningful and legitimate form of identification. While formal diagnosis remains essential for accessing accommodations, the findings of this study suggest that self-diagnosed individuals should not be dismissed outright, particularly in research examining lived experiences. The increasing reliance on social media as a platform for self-diagnosis also warrants further investigation, particularly in understanding the role of digital communities in shaping autism self-awareness. Future research should explore how individuals navigate self-diagnosis, the extent to which their self-assessments align with clinical evaluations, and the potential risks and benefits of this process.

The findings underscore a pressing need for significant reform in autism diagnosis and mental health care provision for autistic females (Hutson & Hutson, 2024). Clinician education must improve to account for the female autism phenotype. Many diagnostic tools, such as the Autism Diagnostic Observation Schedule (ADOS), remain male-centric, contributing to diagnostic disparities (Adamou et al., 2021). Training should focus on recognising camouflaging behaviours, understanding internalised autistic traits, and challenging gendered assumptions about autism. Given the widespread dissatisfaction with traditional therapy models, mental health professionals must also be trained in autistic-friendly therapeutic interventions. This includes adapting therapy environments to reduce sensory stressors, using direct and structured communication styles, and validating autistic identity rather than imposing neurotypical social expectations.

Financial and bureaucratic barriers remain a significant obstacle for many autistic individuals, particularly those who suspect they are autistic but are unable to afford an assessment (Khougar et al., 2023). Future policy efforts should focus on making autism diagnoses more affordable, accessible, and clinician-informed, particularly for those who do not fit the stereotypical male presentation of autism.

LIMITATIONS

The study is limited by its small sample size, surface-level exploration, only subjective data as its basis, and the cross-sectional nature of it. These limitations can be improved upon in future research. Additionally, while this study provides valuable insights, several methodological constraints must be acknowledged. The small sample size restricts the generalisability of the findings, and the subjective nature of self-reported experiences introduces potential biases. Furthermore, the fact that the interviewer and analyst shared a psychology background and familiarity with neurodiverse experiences may have shaped participant responses. However, these limitations are counterbalanced by the study's rich qualitative insights, which provide a foundation for further exploration.

Future research should aim to build upon these findings by conducting larger-scale, cross-cultural studies on autistic females' diagnostic experiences. Additionally, studies should examine the long-term psychological effects of late or missed autism diagnoses, particularly regarding mental health outcomes and quality of life. Another critical area for future research is the intersection between gender identity and autism, given the growing evidence of higher autism prevalence among gender-diverse individuals.

CONCLUSION

This study highlights the systemic failures within autism diagnosis and mental health care for autistic females. While participants expressed a strong sense of identity and Autistic Joy, they also faced widespread clinician dismissal, ineffective therapeutic interventions, and structural barriers to formal diagnosis. The study reinforces the need for urgent reform in clinical training, diagnostic tools, and mental health interventions, particularly in recognising the unique presentation of autism in females.

As Carl Rogers stated, counsellors must be "expert learners" of the client. The findings of this study suggest that clinicians must listen more actively, engage in ongoing education, and approach autistic individuals with greater humility and openness. Only through these changes can mental health care

providers offer truly inclusive and effective support for autistic females, ensuring that their experiences are validated rather than overlooked.

Ultimately, this study calls for a re-evaluation of self-diagnosis, greater inclusivity in autism research, and systemic improvements in autism-related mental health care. Addressing these issues will not only improve diagnostic accuracy but also enhance the overall well-being of autistic individuals who have been historically marginalised within clinical and research settings.

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